

Table 1. Yield and BB scores of PR110 and PR106, Punjab, India, 1988-91.

Year	Trials (no.)	PR110	PR106
<i>Mean yield (t/ha)</i>			
Research trials			
1988	2	7.6	7.4
1989	3	6.8	6.7
1990	4	7.5	7.0
1991	4	7.2	7.0
Mean	13	7.2	7.0
Adaptive trials			
1991	40	6.6	6.5
Overall mean	53	6.7	6.7
<i>BB score^a</i>			
Inoculated under field and artificial conditions			
1988		3	9
1989		3	9
1990		3	9
1991		3	9

^a Scored using the Standard evaluation system for rice.

Table 2. Agronomic and grain quality characters of PR110 and PR106.

Character	PR110	PR106
Plant height (cm)	115	113
Maturity days (no.)	145	145
Panicle-bearing tillers (no./m ²)	391	377
Spikelets (no./panicle)	202	198
Head rice recovery (%)	51.30	51.20
1000-grain wt (g)	17.70	17.90
Grain length (mm)	6.80	6.90
Grain breadth (mm)	1.97	2.04
Length-breadth ratio	3.43	3.38
Grain elongation ratio upon cooking	1.44	1.45
Amylose content (%)	24.70	25.30
Grain appearance	Translucent	Translucent

selected and evaluated for yield, agronomic, and grain quality characters.

Extensive tests showed that PR110 has yield potential equal to that of PR 106 (Table 1).

BB scores (Table 1) show that PR110 maintained its strong BB resistance to the Punjab isolate while PR106 was highly susceptible during 4 yr of testing under field and artificial inoculation conditions.

Agronomic and grain quality characters of PR110 are similar to those of PR 106 (Table 2). □

Hamzu 2, a high-yielding variety suitable for the cool east coastal area of DPR of Korea

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Hamzu 2 is a new rice variety with high and stable yield capacity under the conditions of the cool east coastal area of DPR of Korea.

The growth duration of Hamzu 2 is 172 d, which is 4-5 d shorter than that of check variety Pyongyang 15. Hamzu 2 has 3150 ± 50°C degree days accumulated temperature for growth above 10°C. When this variety was transplanted on 20 May in Hamzu region, it flowered 9-12 Aug and matured 2-5-30 Sep.

Hamzu 2 is 78 cm tall (without panicle), or 7 cm taller than the check. Its flag leaf is erect. Grain type is long-oval, spikelets are awnless, and its color is pale yellow.

Of five recommended varieties in this region, Hamzu 2 showed the highest cold tolerance in farmers' fields when serious cold damage occurred in Aug 1988.

It had the highest grain yield in regional yield trials during 1988-91 (see table); mean yield was 8.5 t/ha over 4 yr. It produced 1.6 t more grain/ha than the check in 1988. Grain number per panicle is significantly higher than that of the check.

Effective level of N fertilizer is 120-140 kg N/ha, and optimum spacing is 20 × 13 cm. Hamzu 2 has multiple resistance to insects and diseases, especially to blast and bacterial blight. □

Performance of Hamzu 2 in regional yield trials in DPR of Korea, 1988-91.

Variety	Panicles (no./hill)	Spikelets (no./panicle)	Filled grains (%)	1000-grain weight (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)
<i>1988</i>					
Hamzu 2	7.3	95.5	78.3	25.8	8.5
Pyongyang 15 (check)	8.7	73.8	64.1	26.5	6.9
<i>1989</i>					
Hamzu 2	7.3	109.2	71.7	28.2	8.6
Pyongyang 15	8.5	69.8	79.3	29.1	7.5
<i>1990</i>					
Hamzu 2	6.8	112.4	74.7	26.5	8.4
Pyongyang 15	7.8	78.9	74.0	27.8	7.6
<i>1991</i>					
Hamzu 2	9.6	79.6	73.7	27.3	8.6
Pyongyang 15	11.1	52.2	80.4	29.1	7.8

Rice germplasm for anaerobic seeding

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A serious constraint in direct seeded rice is unstable crop establishment, which is caused by limited O₂ supply to the germinating seeds in the flooded soil.

Rice varieties that establish well in flooded soil were recently identified. The coleoptile and mesocotyls of these varieties elongate well at low O₂ concentration. Some of the identified varieties originated from deepwater and aus cultures in Northeast India and

Bangladesh. It might be possible to use the varieties in waterlogged rainfed lowlands and in hydromorphic lands in West Africa.

I am collaborating with scientists in national agricultural research systems in Korea, the Philippines, and Vietnam to develop agronomic practices that can best utilize this particular physiological character. I am also testing whether the character can be incorporated into breeding lines.

Rice workers interested in using these varieties for agronomic trials, breeding direct seeded rice, or physiological analysis can obtain detailed information from the author. □